

THE EFFECT OF MICROTEACHING ON PRE-SERVICE TURKISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS' SPEAKING ANXIETIESⁱ

Kenan Bulut¹, Fatma Aık², mer ifti^{3 ii}

¹Asst. Prof. Dr., Yüzüncü Yıl University, Faculty of Education, Van/Turkey

²Prof. Dr., Gazi University, Faculty of Education, Ankara/Turkey

³Asst. Prof. Dr., Yüzüncü Yıl University, Faculty of Education, Van/Turkey

Abstract:

In this study, *microteaching* was tested to improve pre-service Turkish Language teachers' speaking anxieties. The purpose of this study is to reveal the *effect of microteaching on pre-service Turkish Language teachers' speaking anxieties*. This study which was carried out within the context of Speaking Education course was conducted in the spring term of 2014-2015 academic year. The study group of this research which progressed during all the term consists of the students who took Speaking Education course in the term aforesaid in Yuzuncu Yil University, College of Education, Turkish Language Education Department. For this study which was carried on with true experimental design two groups were formed one of them being Experimental Group and the other one being Control Group. While Speaking Education course was given to Experimental Group based upon microteaching, the same course was given traditionally (the continuous teaching style) to Control Group. Pretests and posttests were implemented to both groups for the study and, at the end of the study, not only both groups' interior differences between pretests and posttests were analyzed, but also two groups' difference between posttests was analyzed. In the analysis of data *t-test* were used. Besides, effect size was computed with *Cohen's d*. At the end of the study, it was found that there was a significant decline (from intermediate level to beginner level) in experimental group's speaking anxieties posttest scores while there wasn't any decline in control group's speaking anxieties posttest scores.

Keywords: Pre-service Turkish language teachers, Speaking Education course, microteaching, speaking anxiety

ⁱ This article is adapted from dissertation "The Effect of Microteaching on Pre-Service Turkish Language Teachers' Speaking Skills and Anxieties"

ⁱⁱ Correspondence: email: kenanbulut80@yyu.edu.tr, fatmaacik1@yahoo.com, omerciftci@yyu.edu.tr

Introduction

Human is a social being. Communication with other people is a necessity for social beings. Because, by its very nature, it is impossible for human to live abstracted from others, notably its fellows. "It is unimaginable for individual and community life to continue without agreement between people and sharing the feelings, thoughts and opinions" (Temizkan, 2009, p. 92). The primary goal of communication is to find the least common denominator, exchange feelings by and fulfill the requirements by getting along with one another (Habacı, 2013, p. 265). Speaking which is one of the most obvious characteristics that differentiate human from other beings is an effective tool shaping relationships with other people. Speaking ability is equal with history of humanity. Thus humankind makes an effort to verbalize and transfer the feeling and thoughts to others from day one. Because, "the linguistic skill that allows human to reflect information, thoughts and feelings within the shortest way is speaking" (Arslan and Sevim, 2013, p. 152).

Definitely "speaking is not a simple vocalization process. It contains various mental functions and processes beyond vocalization. For this reason, speaking is also called 'thinking aloud' " (Günes, 2013, p. 106). It is an undeniable fact that it is possible with healthy communication for humankind to be successful in business, education, trade and private life. As for the healthy communication tools, they are rhetoric and apparentness. "We maintain our daily lives and exchange information with people by speaking. Speaking is also a spiritual requirement as a way for expressing feelings such as distress, pleasure and desire" (Özbay, 2005b). "The meaning of the word 'human's faith changes as much as language/ either it heads the country or loses his head' in Kutadgu Bilig reflects the same belief. Down the ages, speaking hasn't lost its value in editing relationships with others and people' interaction (Sever, 2011, p.22).

Individuals want to address correctly and effectively to the interactants, express themselves properly by speaking well, and in this way impress them throughout their personal, business and social lives (Kardaş, 2015, p. 546). However, various obstacles may come into question in the process of achieving the objectives in a speech. Akbayir (2011, p. 13-14) groups these obstacles that are known as basic speech blocks in literature as related to speaker, related to speech, related to audience and related to environment. The number of blocks related to speaker is a good many while varying from person to person. As Sargin (2006, p. 14) states, it is possible to make mention of various factors' effects that affect both public speech and face to face speech negatively arising from individual whereabouts, social, cultural, economic and physical conditions or individual's psychological mode, information and ability inadequacy. Sometimes, it can be seen that people who are well equipped, cultured, exceptionally good in dual conversations abstain from public speech (Gürzap, 2007, p. 140). This case is a lot more

valid for primary students. Because of anxieties like what they say being found odd, being laughed at, being ridiculed, feeling humiliated while speaking; students maintain an extremely timid, diffident stance, trill, have heart palpitations, their mouth go dry while speaking; and consequently they get into panic and want to go back to their place forming the sentences one after another to finish their speech as immediate as possible without lifting their head from the paper. Even though these students are well prepared for the topic, they keep away from focusing on the topic in front of the class. According to Gndz (2007, p. 110) while speech errors are mostly common among primary and secondary students, today, it can also be seen among higher education students.

Here, one of the factors that cause all of these is speech anxiety. "Anxiety is defined as a reaction related to an undetected factor that is present in the environment or person's own individuality, or takes action with the changes in the environment or by unconscious, suppressed force's in the individuality coming into play (Budak, 2000, p. 437). Anxiety that is a spiritual and physical reaction that a person gives under various circumstances is a feeling of extreme concern and panic that the person has difficulty in hindering. "This is one of the paradoxical characteristics of fear reaction; a person's involuntarily going through something that is most scary or disgusting for him/her (Beck, 2006, p. 41). According to Trkapar (2004, p. 13) it might come into question for some sensations in the body to accompany this feeling. According to the researcher, sensations like feeling of chest tightness, pulsation speedup, swelter, headache, emptiness feeling in the stomach and sudden need to use the toilet can be cited. Sometimes uneasy mood, coldness in hands and feet, tremble and chill, restiveness might arise from anxiety. People who experience this feel anxiety such as thinking something bad will happen, being afraid of being humiliated in front of others. Sometimes this feeling can show up unidentifiably.

Anxiety having various degrees from very light to heavy panic is also a feeling that all people can experience from time to time, sometimes while giving a speech, or taking an exam. If it is felt in a normal degree it brings success to the individual. Not feeling any anxiety or feeling it too much is harmful. Sevim (2012, p. 929) states that when different fields of science are examined, some anxiety types such as mathematic anxiety, computer anxiety, social anxiety, chemistry anxiety, career anxiety and writing anxiety are mentioned. As to speaking anxiety being one of the important types of anxiety, it is fear and anxiety state that people experience while giving a public speech. According to ahin and Kana (2013, p. 256) "one of the most difficult things in life is to address to a community. No matter how the speaker is ready for the speech, rostrum scares the speaker most of the time. Whoever goes up to the rostrum to speak gets excited. This excitement may lead to absentmindedness". This affects a quality speech negatively. Thus, such unfavorable cases, particularly speaking anxiety, which starts at young ages should be minimized as immediate as possible. For this, kingpins are

teachers, especially native language teachers. It is important for these teachers whether to graduate from bachelor's program well equipped in this sense or not. As a matter of fact, one of the purposes of Speaking Education course in the Bachelor's Program of Turkish Language Education is to overcome teacher candidates' deficiencies in this sense and ensure them to graduate with wherewithal to be beneficial to the students they will teach.

At this point, to teach the Speaking Education course using various practice based methods and techniques becomes prominent. In the literature review, unfortunately, it is possible to see that practices and studies in this aspect are greatly neglected although being effective to a large extent in people' being accepted in their social environment and having a good reputation. This situation is the starting point of this study. Accordingly, it is thought that to teach the Speaking Education course with microteaching technique would be effective in minimizing teacher candidates ' speaking anxiety.

Microteaching

"Microteaching was developed by Faculty of Education at Stanford University and first applied as a combined training and diagnostic tool in Stanford's teacher intern program in the summer term of 1963" (Allen, 1967, p.1). This technique that has an important role in transferring information into practice has been used in the field of education for about sixty years.

According to Allen (1980) who is the inventor of the technique, microteaching is a technique aimed to equip teacher candidates with teaching skills and improve them in the environments that have restricted time and student and, simulated to real classrooms (Allen cited in akır, 2000, p. 62). While Deniz (1993, p. 32) defines microteaching as "a laboratory method used to simplify the complexity of normal teaching-learning process" Uzunboylu and Hürsen (2010, p. 64) emphasize that it is a technique which particularly helps teacher candidates to overcome the anxiety, fear and deficiencies towards their job.

When implementations are examined microteaching appears to be a technique including implementation of one of the knowledge and skills about teaching in a controlled class and limited time, determining the deficiencies and overcoming these deficiencies and unfavorable cases with various feedback. Richter (2009) figures the model of microteaching technique, also known as a method of feedback (Güney and Semerci, 2009, p. 77), as following:

Figure 1. The process of microteaching technique (Richter, 2009)

According to the figure, first, teaching the lesson comes into question. Then, the critics of the lesson, speech is made. In the meanwhile, constructive feedback has great importance. The teacher candidate practices again in the light of these feedbacks and critics.

There exist studies that mention about some negative sides of this technique along with its many advantages. Klahci (1994) and Kazu (1996) explain such unfavorable cases as not teaching the lesson in real classrooms, having limited time and students' not being real. This research lasted during a class period and was conducted with real students. Additionally, the limitations which come into question in microteaching like classes' being short were out of question. As the research lasted during a class period, each student made speech at least four times and video recorded. The term of *expanded microteaching technique* is used for such implementations (Peker, 2009, p. 874).

After 1980's, microteaching technique has been used more functionally and commonly in the Western countries. This technique which we acquainted with a lot later than Western countries is still limited to few numbers of implementations in our country.

No study about the effect of microteaching technique on reducing students', teacher candidates' and teachers' speaking anxiety was found in the native and foreign literature. This makes this study important.

The aim of this study is to reveal *microteaching technique's utility in its implementation in the Speaking Education course by examining its effect on reducing Turkish Language teacher candidates' speaking anxiety*. Within the frame of this aim, answers for the following two basic questions were sought:

1. What is the level of *difference* and *effect size* between Experimental and Control Group teacher candidates' *public speech anxiety* before and after the lesson? (Within groups)
2. What is the level of *difference* and *effect size* between Experimental and Control Group teacher candidates' *public speech anxiety* before and after the lesson? (Among groups)

Method

Research Model

In this study experimental design was used. Experimental designs are “research models that the data wanted to be observed is generated directly under the control of the researcher with the purpose of defining cause and effect relationship” (Karasar, 2014, p. 87). “Experimental researches are the ones in all scientific methods that the most certain results are obtained. Because researcher implements comparable processes and then examines their effects, it is expected from such studies’ results to lead the researcher to the most certain comments (Büyüköztürk, Çakmak, Akgün, Karadeniz and Demirel, 2008, p. 12). The study was conducted with “true experimental design” which is the strongest among experimental designs and has the most scientific value. In this study, data was collected with quantitative research method. For this, a quantitative data collection tool (anxiety survey) was used.

Study Group

This study was conducted within the Speaking Education course in the Bachelor’s Program of Turkish Language Education in the spring term of junior year. The students who were taking this class in the Turkish Language Education Program in Yuzuncu Yil University, Faculty of Education in the Spring Term of 2014-2015 academic year composed the study group.

Forming the Groups

Two groups were formed one of them being Experimental Group and the other Control Group for the study which lasted a class period. The groups were formed equally at the beginning of the term with 30 students who took the class taking the gender factor into account. It was statistically defined that there were no significant pre-test differences between groups (Table 3). According to the data collected from the groups which undergone the post-tests at the end of the term both pre-test and post-test differences within each group and post-test differences among each group were examined. The study design is as following:

Table 1. Study design

Groups	Before the study (pre-test)	During the study	After the study (post-test)
Experimental Group	- Speaking Anxiety Survey for Teacher Candidates	- <i>Speaking Education course based on microteaching technique</i>	- Speaking Anxiety Survey for Teacher Candidates

Control Group	-	Speaking Anxiety Survey for Teacher Candidates	-	Speaking Education course according to traditional method	-	Speaking Anxiety Survey for Teacher Candidates
----------------------	---	--	---	---	---	---

Instruments, Validity, Reliability

Speaking Anxiety Survey for Teacher Candidates developed by Sevim (2012) was used for this study. The survey comprises three factors: 1. Speaker Focused Anxiety, 2. Environment Focused Anxiety, 3. Speaking Psychology. Speech Focused Anxiety factor has 11, Environment Focused Anxiety has 6, Speaking Psychology factor has 3 items.

Validity (content and construct validity) and reliability (Cronbach's alpha) studies were conducted by the researcher. Cronbach's alpha factor was examined again with a pre-implementation and also confirmatory factor analysis was measured for this study. The Cronbach's alpha factors that were obtained from the measurements of pre-tests and post-tests of the real study were examined separately. It was clearly seen that measurement scores of both the researcher who developed the survey and this study's researcher obtained were all fine and the reliability of the survey was at a high level.

In this study, it is aimed to evaluate the anxiety levels of teacher candidates as a whole. Thus, total results of all items that form the survey were examined, sub-factors were not evaluated separately.

Data Collection

The data constituting "pre-test" was collected with anxiety survey from the study group mentioned above at the first week of the term. At the last week of the study that lasted a class period, the data constituting "post-test" was collected with again the same instrument. The differences between teacher candidates' speaking anxiety and their effect size were measured with the data collected.

Data Analysis

While examining the distribution of the results of the test for this study, skewness and kurtosis values were taken into consideration. According to Kline (2005, p. 63), in order to accept a test as having a normal distribution, it is enough for skewness value to be between -3, +3 and kurtosis value be smaller than 10. On this respect, it is accepted for the results of this study to have normal distribution. IBM SPSS Statistics (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) 21.0 Program was used for the data analysis. While analyzing the results, the pre-test and post-test differences within groups were measured by *Paired Samples T-Test*, the pre-test and post-test differences among groups were measured by *Independent Samples T-Test*.

Additionally, in this study, effect sizes between tests were found to be significant findings. Shortly, effect size "is the statistical value which shows the deviation level from the expectations identified in the null hypothesis of the results obtained from the sample" (Cohen; Vacha-Haasse and Thompson cited in zsoy and zsoy, 2013, p. 337). In other words, it is how a newly tried method makes difference compared to the old one (Yıldırım and Yıldırım, 2011, p. 1119). As t-tests were used in this study, Cohen's measurement was used for effect sizes. Cohen (1988) states that size effect of d value up to 0,20 can be assessed as "weak", around 0,50 can be assessed as "medium", higher than 0,80 can be assessed as "strong", 1 and higher than 1 can be assessed as "very strong" (Cohen cited in Işık, 2014, p. 67).

Findings

Findings Related to Pre-Test and Post-Test Differences and Effect Sizes Within Experimental Group and Control Group Teacher Candidates

Statistics about information in question are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Paired samples t-test measurements of pre-test and post-test differences of Experimental Group and Control Group teacher candidates (within groups) and effect sizes (According to scores obtained from SASTC)

Groups	N	$\bar{X}$		S		sd	T	p	Cohen's d
		Pre-test	Post- test	Pre-test	Post- test				
Experimental Group	15	54,60	49,73	9,68	8,18	14	2,68	,018	-0,54 ⁱⁱⁱ
Control Group	15	53,53	54,46	13,60	11,00	14	-,33	,743	0,07

SASTC: Speaking Anxiety Survey for Teacher Candidates

According to the first line of the table above there is a statistically significant difference between pre-tests and post-tests of Experimental Group teacher candidates who took the Speaking Education course with microteaching technique, and thus it is possible to say that there is a significant reduction in their "public speech anxiety" [$t_{(14)} = 2,689$, $p < ,05$ ($p = ,018$)]. When all items of anxiety survey are examined in total, while speaking anxiety average score in the teacher candidates' pre-tests which were applied at the beginning of the term was $\bar{X} = 54,60$, it reduced to $\bar{X} = 49,73$ after microteaching practice.

ⁱⁱⁱ Anxiety Survey is used to reveal whether teacher candidates' anxiety average of post tests reduces or not compared to pre-tests. If average scores reduce, it is concluded that anxiety level of teacher candidates reduces and thus the training provided to them is successful. When anxiety averages reduce effect size has a "- "value; when anxiety averages increase effect size has a "+ "value. If the effect values in the tables that shows findings about anxiety survey are "- ", it is a positive finding; if they are "+ " it is a negative finding.

This reduction means that *the medium-level anxiety of teacher candidates who took the Speaking Education course with microteaching technique reduced to lower level*. As Sevim (2014, p. 737) states, 20-52 score interval infers low anxiety and 69-100 score interval infers high anxiety. Accordingly, 53-68 score interval infers medium-level anxiety.

When the second line of table is examined, according to total scores, it is apparent that *there is not a significant difference* between pre-tests and post-tests of Control Group teacher candidates who took the Speaking Education course with traditional methods throughout a class period, therefore there is not a significant reduction in their speaking anxiety [$t_{(14)} = -,33, p > ,05 (p = ,743)$]. While speaking anxiety average score in the teacher candidates' pre-tests which were applied at the beginning of the term is $\bar{X} = 53,53$, there is not a reduction of the average after taking the course with traditional method, on the contrary, there is little increase (about 1 point): $\bar{X} = 54,46$. This finding shows that traditional method has no significant effect in reducing speaking anxiety, contrarily, it may increase the anxiety.

When the effect size values at the last line of table above (Table 2) is examined, effect size of Experimental Group who took the Speaking Education course with microteaching technique is measured as -0,54. This value's being higher than -0,20 (especially being among -0,50) shows that *there is a medium-level effect size between Experimental Group's pre-test and post-test*. In spite of this, effect size of Control Group who took the Speaking Education course with traditional method is measured as 0,07. As this value is less than -0,20, it is possible to say that *the effect size (0,07) between Control Group's pre-test and post-test is very low*.

Findings Related to Pre-Tests And Post-Tests Differences and Effect Sizes Among Experimental Group and Control Group Teacher Candidates

Pre-test differences among groups are measured as well as post test differences. Statistical information about findings is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Independent samples t-test measurements of pre-test and post-test differences among Experimental Group and Control Group teacher candidates and effect sizes (According to scores obtained from SASTC)

Pre-test							
Groups	N	$\bar{X}$	S	sd	t	p	Cohen's d
Experimental Group	15	54,60	9,68	28	,24	,806	0,09
Control Group	15	53,53	13,60				
Post-test							
Experimental Group	15	49,73	8,18	28	-1,33	,192	-0,48
Control Group	15	54,46	11,00				

SASTC: Speaking Anxiety Survey for Teacher Candidates

According to first part of the table (pre-test), in terms of total score of anxiety survey, *there isn't a significant difference* between pre-tests of Experimental Group who takes the Speaking Education course with microteaching technique and Control Group who takes the Speaking Education course with traditional method [$t_{(28)} = ,24$, $p > ,05$ ($p = ,806$)].

While Experimental Group's speaking anxiety average score in the teacher candidates' pre-tests which were applied at the beginning of the term is $\bar{X} = 54,60$, Control Group's speaking anxiety average score in the teacher candidates' pre-tests which were applied at the beginning of the term is $\bar{X} = 53,53$. It clearly appears that there isn't a significant difference in pre-test between groups.

In previous findings, it was stated that there is a significant difference between Experimental Group's pre-tests and post-tests, however there isn't a significant difference between Control Group's pre-tests and post-tests (Table 2), and this is because of microteaching technique's effect applied in the Experimental Group.

When the table above (Table 3) is examined, it is apparent that, in terms of post tests, there is a significant difference between Experimental Group who took the Speaking Education course with microteaching technique and Control Group who took the Speaking Education course with traditional method, however this is not a statistically significant difference [$t_{(28)} = -1,337$, $p > ,05$ ($p = ,192$)]. When average scores are examined in terms of anxiety survey total scores, while average anxiety of Experimental Group reduces from 56,40 to 49,73; average anxiety of Control Group increases from 53,53 to 54,46. Accordingly, while anxiety level of Experimental Group reduces in post-tests, in Control Group, anxiety score in post-tests increases even if just a bit.

According to effect size values in the last line of table above (Table 3) containing Experimental Group and Control Group pre-test and post-test anxiety average scores, when examined in terms of total score of all items in the survey, effect size between pre-tests of Experimental Group who took the Speaking Education course with microteaching technique and Control Group who took the Speaking Education course with traditional method appears to be of *very "low" level* (0.09). In spite of this, effect size between post-tests of Experimental Group and Control Group is measured as -0,48. This finding shows that there is a medium-level effect between post-tests of two groups. When findings above are considered as a whole, a significant reduction in speaking anxiety happens in case of teacher candidates' taking Speaking Education course with microteaching technique. Additionally, it appears to be that, generally, there isn't a reduction in speaking anxiety after taking Speaking Education course with traditional method. This reveals that microteaching technique has a significant effect on reducing speaking anxiety.

Results and Discussion

General Results of the Study

1. *Significant difference in favours of post-test (,018) and effect size (-0,54)* between Experimental Group teacher candidates' public speech anxiety before and after taking the Speaking Education course with microteaching technique were found out.
2. *Significant difference (,734) and effect size (0,07)* between Control Group teacher candidates' public speech anxiety before and after taking the Speaking Education course with traditional method were not found out.
3. *Significant difference (,806) and effect size (0,97)* between Experimental Group teacher candidates' and Control Group teacher candidates' public speech anxiety before taking Speaking Education course were not found out.
4. *Significant difference (,192)* between Experimental Group teacher candidates' who took the Speaking Education course with microteaching technique and Control Group teacher candidates' who took the Speaking Education course with traditional method public speech anxiety was not found out, however *effect size (-0,48)* was found out.

Discussion

As no study about the effect of microteaching technique on speaking anxiety was found in the related literature, other studies about teacher training examining microteaching technique's effects were benefited from in comparisons and discussion in this section.

Results above obtained from Speaking Anxiety Survey for Teacher Candidates are found out by measurement of total scores that teacher candidates obtained from the survey. Accordingly, significant difference in favours of post-test (,018) and effect size (-0,54) between Experimental Group teacher candidates' pre-tests and post-tests were found out. In spite of this, *significant difference (,734) and effect size (0,07)* between Control Group teacher candidates' pre-tests and post-tests were not found out. This means that a significant reduction in speaking anxiety happens in case of teacher candidates' taking Speaking Education course with microteaching technique.

Arslan (2012, p. 228) asked teacher candidates' opinion in his study *University Students' Various Opinions about "Public Speech"*. According to results of this study, teacher candidates stated that they felt numerous anxieties about "public speech" like *being afraid of forgetting the words or forgetting them, anxiety of confusing the words, anxiety of fainting*. In Basaran and Erdem (2009, p. 751)'s study, teacher candidates stated that *anxiety (goof, forgetting the words, declamation to public)* is one of the biggest obstacles that hinders elocution most. It is one of the important duties of education to minimize such

anxieties that teachers state before entering to the profession. This can be actualized only if various techniques are implemented. Microteaching is an important technique in overcoming problems in question. According to Guven (2011, p. 206), "purpose of microteaching is to transfer teacher candidates' knowledge and skills into practice, provide them with experience with usage of various skills, improve their research skills, enhance their self-confidence, *reduce their anxiety level* and enable them to evaluate themselves. In almost all studies it is concluded that microteaching practices reduce various anxieties that teacher candidates feel despite the fact that the number of native and foreign researches about the topic in question is limited. This study overlaps with results of the studies found throughout the literature review.

As Ghafoor et al. (2012) emphasize in their study that microteaching technique reduces mathematics teacher candidates' anxiety, Kallenbach and Gall (1969) confirmed in their study that teacher candidates' uneasiness related to the first lesson was reduced to a large extent with microteaching technique (Kallenbach and Gall cited in Kazu, 1996, p. 67). Yoğurtu (2009, p. 68) states that "in evaluation of linguistic performances, for taking such factors especially as *anxiety*, motivation into consideration, it should be emphasized that microteaching approach has characteristics that allow student performances to improve by real experiences" in his study.

Teacher candidates are asked for their opinions about microteaching's contributions to their teaching skills, in-field information and in-field education information (Atav et al., 2006, p. 10) and its meeting expectations for the First Reading and Writing class and its contributions to it (Karadağ and Akkaya, 2013, p. 47-54). Teacher candidates stated that microteaching practices *reduced their anxieties* about these issues. It is also emphasized in various studies that teacher candidates state that microteaching reduces anxiety and this is one of the positive sides of the technique (Atav et al., 2006, p. 7-11; Erdem et al., 2012).

Sarı et al. (2005) stated in their study that students' *anxiety* in using class materials *reduced* after microteaching. Additionally, researchers stated that "the groups' anxiety reduced after microteaching by planned rehearsals before real lecturing". In the same study, when the answers to the item *I'm afraid of forgetting the words while lecturing* are examined, while forgetting anxiety existed before microteaching, there was a significant reduction in the number of teacher candidates who stated that they had forgetting anxiety after microteaching.

Erkten and Durkan (2009) revealed in their study that students were anxious before starting microteaching practices in Special Teaching Methods 2 class, however, after practices these *anxieties reduced*. Grgen (2003, p. 63) states that teacher candidates overcome a number o anxieties while lecturing by means of microteaching. Uzunboylu and Hrsen (2010, p. 64) points out that microteaching is a technique that especially contributes to overcome teacher candidates' professional *anxieties*, fears and

deficiencies. Marulcu and Dedetürk (2014, p. 368) stated that microteaching practices reduce *teacher candidates' anxiety about classroom management* which is one of the various unfavorable cases determined.

In these studies, all results about the reduction in teacher candidates' anxieties by means of microteaching technique overlap with results obtained in this study from various aspects. Because a significant reduction in anxiety scores of Experimental Group teacher candidates happened in this study. This situation which is supported by literature shows that microteaching technique not only improves teacher candidates' speaking skills (Bulut, 2015), but also has a significant influence on reducing their anxieties.

Suggestions

- Anxiety is not just a “speaking” case, it shows itself in other linguistic skills like reading and writing. Especially “writing anxiety” appears to be a case found to a large extent in the literature. So, it is essential for the lessons in Turkish Language Education Programs to be taught more practice-based moving away from theoretic approach and this should be emphasized sensitively.
- Ongoing educational system and socio-cultural structure of our society leads high speaking anxiety in a great deal of society including educated individuals. It is possible to say that efforts to minimize this unfavorable situation are limited. Thus, it is necessary to create awareness, have thought, develop attitude and show an approach about this situation's importance especially for teacher candidates. Results above shows that microteaching technique is appropriate for this.
- Actually, this technique should be frequently used in Oral Expression, Effective Communication Skills, Turkish Grammar, Classroom Management, Special Teaching Methods, Principles and Methods of Teaching and Drama classes in Faculties of Education as well as practicing it frequently in School Experience and Teaching Practice classes as it is a technique that promotes student-centered education.
- Feedback is an essential part of this technique. Thus, it is essential to be careful throughout criticism and to do collective evaluations at the end of each lesson. Any contrary case increases anxiety level of students.
- For applicability of such techniques which entails more practice, it is thought that Speaking Education course should be taught at least two terms and it is necessary for classroom sizes to be limited by 25-30 students which is ideal. When it is impossible, the students should be grouped in practice lessons and thus practice opportunities can be enhanced.

- Technological substructure should be sufficient to practice microteaching comfortably. So it would be beneficial to arrange “equipped classrooms” which have appropriate acoustic environment as well as necessary tools and physical conditions as needed.
- Results of this study were obtained by comparing Speaking Education course which was taught by microteaching technique and Speaking Education course which was taught by traditional method. It is thought that different techniques are/might be effective in reducing Turkish Language teacher candidates' speaking anxiety. Studies aimed at comparing this technique with other techniques may be conducted.

References

1. Akbayır, S. (2011). *Sözlü Anlatım - Nasıl Konuşabilirim?* Ankara: Pegem Akademi.
2. Allen, D. W. (1967). Preface. Dwight W. Allen (Ed.). *Micro-teaching: A Description* içinde Preface.
3. Arslan, A. (2012). Üniversite öğrencilerinin “topluluk karşısında konuşma” ile ilgili çeşitli görüşleri (Ağrı İbrahim Çeçen Üniversitesi örneği). *Turkish Studies International Periodical For the Languages, Literature and History of Turkish or Turkic*, 7(3-Summer), 221-231.
4. Arslan, A. & Sevim, O. (2013). Konuşma becerisinin geliştirilmesinde kullanılabilecek etkinlik örnekleri. Aziz Kılınç & Abdullah Şahin (Ed.). *Konuşma Eğitimi* içinde (s. 151-180). Ankara: Pegem Akademi.
5. Atav, E., Kunduz, N. & Seçken, N. (2014). Biyoloji eğitiminde mikro öğretim uygulamalarına dair öğretmen adaylarının görüşleri. *Hacettepe Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 29(4), 1-15.
6. Başaran, M. & Erdem, İ. (2009). Öğretmen adaylarının güzel konuşma becerisi ile ilgili görüşleri üzerine bir araştırma. *Kastamonu Eğitim Dergisi*, 17(3), 743-754.
7. Beck, A. T. (2006). Teorik ve klinik bakış açıları. *Anksiyete Bozuklukları ve Fobiler* (V. Öztürk, Çev.) içinde. İstanbul: Litera.
8. Budak, S. (2000). *Psikoloji Sözlüğü*. Ankara: Bilim ve Sanat.
9. Bulut, K. (2015). *Mikro öğretim tekniğinin Türkçe öğretmen adaylarının konuşma beceri ve kaygılarına etkisi*. Doktora Tezi, Gazi Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Ankara.
10. Büyüköztürk, Ş., Çakmak, E. K., Akgün, Ö. E., Karadeniz, Ş. & Demirel, F. (2008). *Bilimsel Araştırma Yöntemleri*. Ankara: Pegem Akademi.

11. akır, . S. (2000). ğretmen yetiřtirmede teoriyi pratięe baęlayan mikro ğretimin Trkiye'deki  üniversitede durumu. *Hacettepe niversitesi Eęitim Fakltesi Dergisi*, 7, 62-68.
12. Deniz, L. (1993). Mikro ğretim - ğretme becerilerini kazandırmada bir yntem-. *Marmara niversitesi Eęitim Fakltesi Dergisi*, 5, 31-46.
13. Erdem, E., Erdoęan, . I., zyalın Oskay, . & Yılmaz, A. (2012, Haziran). *Kimya eęitiminde mikro ğretim ynteminin etkililięi ve ęrenci grřleri*. X. Ulusal Fen Bilimleri ve Matematik Eęitimi Kongresi'nde sunulmuř bildiri. Orta Doęu Teknik niversitesi (ODT), Ankara.
14. Erkten, S. & Durkan, N. (2009, Mayıs). *zelğretim yntemleri II dersinde mikro ğretim uygulamaları*. I. Uluslararası Trkiye Eęitim Arařtırmaları Kongresi'nde sunulmuř bildiri, anakkale 18 Mart niversitesi, anakkale.
15. Ghafoor, A., Kiani, A., Kayani, S. & Kayani, S. (2012). An exploratory study of microteaching as an effective technology. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(4-Special Issue), 224-238.
16. Grgen, İ. (2003). Mikro ğretim uygulamasının ğretmen adaylarının sınıfta ders anlatımına iliřkin grřleri zerine etkisi. *Hacettepe niversitesi Eęitim Fakltesi Dergisi*, 24, 56-63.
17. Gndz, O. (2007). Konuřma eęitimi. Ahmet Kırkkılı & Hayati Akyol (Ed.). *İlkğretimde Trke ğretimi iinde* (s. 93-147). Ankara: Pegem A.
18. Gneř, F. (2013). *Trke ğretimi Yaklařımlar ve Modeller*. Ankara: Pegem Akademi
19. Gney, K. & Semerci, . (2009). Mikro-yansıtıcı ğretim ynteminin ğretmen adaylarının yansıtıcı dřnmesine etkisi. *Doęu Anadolu Blgesi arařtırmaları*. 77-83.
20. Grzap, C. (2007). *Sz Syleme ve Diksiyon*. İstanbul: Remzi Kitabevi.
21. Gven, M. (2011). Programda ğretme - ğrenme sreci. Bilal Duman (Ed.). *ğretim İlke ve Yntemleri iinde* (s. 151-264). Ankara: Anı.
22. Habacı, İ. (2013). Etkili eęitim ynteminde iletiřim ve konuřma faktr. Aziz Kılın & Abdullah řahin (Ed.). *Konuřma Eęitimi iinde* (s. 265-276). Ankara: Pegem Akademi.
23. Iřık, İ. (2014). Yokluk hipotezi anlamlılık testi ve etki byklę tartıřmalarının psikoloji arařtırmalarına yansımaları. *Eleřtirel Psikoloji Blteni*, 5, 55-80.
24. Karadaę, R. & Akkaya, A. (2013). İlk okuma yazma ğretimi dersinde mikro ğretim uygulamalarına iliřkin ğretmen adaylarının grřleri. *Ahi Evran niversitesi Kırřehir Eęitim Fakltesi Dergisi (KEFAD)*, 14(2), 39-59.
25. Karasar, N. (2014). *Bilimsel Arařtırma Yntemi - Kavramlar İlkeler Teknikler*. Ankara: Nobel.

26. Kardaş, M. N. (2015). İkinci dili Türkçe olan çok dilli türkçe öğretmeni adaylarının Türkçe konuşma kaygıları ve bu kaygılarının bazı değişkenlerle ilişkisi. *Turkish Studies International Periodical For the Languages, Literature and History of Turkish or Turkic*, 10(7-Spring), 541-556.
27. Kazu, H. (1996). Öğretmen yetiştirmede mikro öğretim yönetimini etkililiği (F.Ü.Teknik Eğitim Fakültesi örneği). Doktora Tezi, Fırat Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Elazığ.
28. Kline, R. B. (2005). *Principles and Practice of Structural Equation Modeling*. New York, ABD: The Guilford Press.
29. Külahçı, Ş. G. (1994). Mikro öğretimde Fırat Üniversitesi Teknik Eğitim Fakültesi deneyimi II. değerlendirme. *Eğitim ve Bilim*, 18(92), 36-44.
30. Marulcu, İ. & Dedetürk, A. (2014). Fen Bilgisi öğretmen adaylarının mikro-öğretim yöntemini uygulamaları: bir eylem araştırması. *Mustafa Kemal Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 11(25), 353-372.
31. Özbay, M. (2005b). Sesle ilgili kavramlar ve konuşma eğitimi. *Milli Eğitim*, 168-Güz, 116-125.
32. Özsoy, S. ve Özsoy, G. (213). Eğitim araştırmalarında etki büyüklüğü raporlanması. *İlköğretim Online*, 12(2), 334-346.
33. Peker, M. (2009). The use of expanded microteaching for reducing preserviceteachers' teaching anxiety about mathematics. *Scientific Research and Essay*, 4(9), 872-880.
34. Richter, S. (2009.). Microteaching. 12 Şubat 2015 tarihinde <http://facdevblog.niu.edu/microteaching> sayfasından erişilmiştir.
35. Sargın, M. (2006). İlköğretim öğrencilerinin konuşma becerilerinin değerlendirilmesi - Muğla ili örneğinde. Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Muğla Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Muğla.
36. Sarı, Y., Sakal, M. & Deniz, S. (2005, Şubat). Okul öncesi öğretmen yetiştirmede mikro öğretim yönteminin etkililiği, Akademik Bilişim Konferansı'nda sunulmuş bildiri, Gaziantep Üniversitesi, Gaziantep.
37. Sever, S. (2011). *Türkçe Öğretimi ve Tam Öğrenme*. Ankara: Anı.
38. Sevim, O. (2012). Öğretmen adaylarına yönelik konuşma kaygısı ölçeği: bir geçerlik ve güvenirlik çalışması. *Turkish Studies International Periodical For the Languages, Literature and History of Turkish or Turkic*, 7(2-Spring), 927-937.
39. Şahin, A. & Kana, F. (2013). Konuşma kaygısı. Aziz Kılınç & Abdullah Şahin (Ed.). *Konuşma Eğitimi içinde* (s. 251-263). Ankara: Pegem Akademi.
40. Temizkan, M. (2009). Akran değerlendirmenin konuşma becerisinin geliştirilmesi üzerindeki etkisi. *Mustafa Kemal Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 6(12), 90-112.

41. Türkçapar, H. (2004). Anksiyete bozukluğu ve depresyonun tanısal ilişkileri. *Klinik Psikiyatri, Ek 4*, 12-16.
42. Uzunboylu, H. & Hürsen, Ç. (2010). *Öğretim İlke ve Yöntemleri*. Ankara: Pegem Akademi.
43. Yıldırım, H. H. & Yıldırım, S. (2011). Hipotez testi, güven aralığı, etki büyüklüğü ve merkezi olmayan olasılık dağılımları üzerine. *Elementary Education Online*, 10(3), 112-123.
44. Yoğurtçu, K. (2009). Türkçenin yabancı dil olarak öğretiminde "mikro öğretim tekniği": Kırgızistan-Türkiye Manas Üniversitesi hazırlık sınıflarında karşılaştırmalı bir çalışma. *Dil Dergisi*, 146, 49-70.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Education Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).